

Sensor integration alters biomechanical load transfer in pressure mapping of neonatal support surfaces

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Abstract

In bedridden patients, the constant load between the body and the support surface increases the risk of soft tissue injuries. Understanding body-mattress interactions is key to developing pressure-reducing support surfaces. Sensors at the material-body interface provide crucial information but may alter interactions by changing local mechanics. To assess such effects, a pressure sensor mat applied on top of support surfaces was compared to point pressure sensors applied on the body surface. We investigated local interface pressure at the occiput and hip on two support surfaces (foam and air-filled mattress), using three newborn weight models (1.3kg, 2.3kg, and 3.3kg) and multiple air pressures (0.2-0.8kPa). The sensor mat led to altered material-body interactions and underestimated interface pressure. Low air pressures (0.2-0.4 kPa) reduced interface pressure below foam mattress levels. Increasing body weight was associated with higher optimal air pressure, indicating the need for weight-specific air pressure adjustment. Exponential regression identified weight-dependent air pressures that minimize interface pressure. Fitted curve coefficients reflected local anatomical and mechanical differences: the hip showed a higher predicted minimum interface pressure and a narrower air pressure tolerance range than the occiput. These findings demonstrate that anatomical region- and weight-specific air pressure protocols are necessary to minimize interface pressure.

Introduction

Immobilized patients experience sustained loads on exposed anatomical areas, such as the hip, legs, back, and head, with increased risk of soft tissue injuries [1], [2]. Preterm neonates are particularly at risk, as their skin has not matured fully and undergoes massive changes as an adaptation to the new, harsh, and dry external environment [3], [4], [5]. Therefore, the immature skin needs to be targeted differently when developing pressure-related preventive devices than for the older infant or adult population [6].

An in-depth understanding of material-body interactions is required to optimize support surfaces and reduce local pressure impact. Most existing products have been tailored for adult biomechanics and body mass and are not directly scalable to infants or neonatal applications. Miniaturizing adult systems often results in a mechanical mismatch, as they do not account for the low body weight, the altered distribution of body weight, particularly the larger weight proportion of the head, and the thin, immature skin of neonates [7]. These characteristics require softer surfaces and more adaptable local support of mattresses. Specialized anti-decubitus mattresses for infants exist, but few are specifically tailored to the needs of lower-weight newborns and early infants. The limited availability likely reflects the small patient population and the considerable heterogeneity in body weight and clinical requirements. As a result, evidence supporting their effectiveness in preventing pressure ulcers in this vulnerable group remains scarce [8], [9], [10], [11].

Products for support surfaces include generic and high-specification foam mattresses, dynamic alternating air mattresses, low-air-loss systems, gel-filled overlays, and sheepskin or fiber-based pads [8]. Currently, foam mattresses remain the product of choice due to their ease of application for this heterogeneous patient group. Ongoing development is being conducted on air mattresses that have the ability to conform faster to the body shape and provide immediate and even support, which specifically relieves pressure on high-risk body sites prone to PUs [12], [13]. Studies have evaluated the efficacy of support surfaces based on various parameters related to comfort or local interface pressure reduction [14]. Interface pressure can be quantified non-invasively, using sensors between the subject and the support surface [15]. Although it captures only external loading, this load directly influences subsurface tissue stress and may contribute to tissue deformation. Interface pressure does not reflect internal stress distributions in detail [16] but remains the most practical and consistent parameter for comparing support surfaces and estimating pressure ulcer risk in heterogeneous patient groups [17], [18].

Flexible sensor mats have been used in both laboratory and clinical studies to assess interface pressure through spatial pressure mapping [12], [19], [20], [21]. However, placing the sensor between the body and the support surface introduces an intermediate layer that may alter surface stiffness, load distribution, and the material-body interaction itself. This may induce a hammocking effect, caused by limited flexibility and elasticity, leading to poor anatomical conformation [22]. As a result, impact force may be redistributed laterally, which reduces peak forces that would be present without the additional layer [23]. These distortions are especially pronounced over curved or bony regions like the occiput or heels. Understanding the influence of specific sensor mats on interface pressure measurements remains a relevant and unresolved question.

In the study presented here, we investigated the influence of pressure sensor mats on interface pressure measurements across different support surfaces, focusing on neonatal settings. By comparing measurements obtained with and without the sensor mat under controlled conditions, we quantify mechanical

interferences introduced by the sensing layer in dependence of the anatomical region, body weight, and air pressure conditions. This is achieved by using point pressure sensors placed at the skin surface. In addition, the sensor placement at the skin level aims to approximate real interface pressure and, thereby, contributes to a critical evaluation of measurement methods used *in vivo*, being pressure sensor mats.

Methods

The primary analyzed parameter was the mean interface pressure at the occiput and hip region. The interface pressure was recorded by a pressure sensor mat applied on top of the support surface and by pressure point sensors attached to the body surface of a neonatal doll. Relative differences between foam and air mattress conditions were assessed and compared.

Experimental setup

Interface pressure was evaluated under controlled laboratory conditions using a neonatal doll (Figure 1) to replicate realistic clinical loadings. The neonatal model doll is a commercially available male newborn care simulator (3B Scientific Baby Care Model, Art.-No.1005088, The Doll Factory). It replicates a full-term neonate with anatomically accurate size. Its weight is 1.3 kg. The rubber shell is harder than neonatal skin and soft tissue. Therefore, it represents a worst-case scenario for pressure ulcer development, where minimal soft tissue buffers bony prominences. In all experiments, the support surfaces and pressure sensor mat were covered by an absorbent sheet (Curea Medical GmbH, Steinfurt, Germany) to provide a covering like in a realistic scenario.

Figure 1: Measurement setup with sensors showing the placement of the point sensor [A], the measurement setup including the neonatal doll with 1kg of additional weight (total 2.3 kg), proportionally distributed [B], and the measurement setup in a replica of a clinical neonatology station bed frame with the air mattress [C].

Instrumentation and pressure calculation

Piezoresistive point pressure sensors (FlexiForce A201, Tekscan Inc., Boston, MA, USA) were applied as reference sensors at the body surface (occiput and hip) and remained in place throughout all measurements. Interface pressure was measured under two conditions: without the sensor mat and with the sensor mat applied (capacitive pressure sensor mat LX100, XSENSOR Technology Corporation, Calgary, AB, Canada). The latter reflects the clinical setting, where only a full-surface interface pressure sensor mat can be used, as point sensors are not applicable in practice. Interface pressure (kPa) was computed by dividing the measured normal force (N) by the defined sensor area (0.713 cm^2). Each FlexiForce sensor was preconditioned at 110% of maximum load, then equilibrated and three-point calibrated using the PB100F device for a sensing range of 0-16kPa and <3% full-scale accuracy [24]. Force was recorded by the sensor during 6.25s at a sampling rate of 8 Hz, resulting in 50 data points. All 50 consecutive interface pressure values were averaged to obtain one value per measurement and sensor. Up to 11 repetitions were acquired in advance whenever signal artefacts were observed during data acquisition or when experimental time allowed. At least four valid measurements were conducted per condition. All measurements were planned prospectively, and all completed and valid trials were included in the analysis.

The capacitive pressure sensor mat recorded interface pressure continuously across the entire contact surface at a spatial resolution of 3.9 sensels/cm² (50x80cm, 160x100 sensels) The pressure sensor mat was factory-calibrated without need for additional calibration or equilibration, with a measurable pressure range of 0.7–27 kPa and an accuracy of ±5% full scale.

A measurement consisted of 50 consecutive data matrices recorded at 2Hz. In each of these data matrices, the highest average of two adjacent sensels in the hip and the occiput region was used to represent the peak interface pressure. This approach reduces sensitivity to artefacts affecting single sensels while maintaining spatial precision. Two adjacent sensels correspond to a contact area of 0.5 cm², consistent with focal loading over small anatomical structures. The number and procedure of repeated measurements were identical to those described previously for point sensor recordings.

Two support surfaces were tested:

- Foam mattress: tested once per doll weight as a reference condition. Technical details: A clinical neonatal foam mattress (Softbed Babytherm, Drägerwerk AG & Co. KGaA, Lübeck, Germany), classified as a class I medical device (GMDN 35183), was used as a reference. It is routinely used in neonatal intensive care
- Air mattress: tested at four discrete air pressure levels and doll weights. Technical details: air mattress was developed at Empa (St. Gallen, Switzerland) and consists of three independent air compartments (head, trunk, legs). It was laser-welded from two TPU sheets (FT1029 Provecta Aromatic, 0.3 mm, DingZing Advanced Materials Inc. The supplier was Scheidegger Polyart GmbH, Huttwil, Switzerland). Dimensions range from 780 × 510 mm (deflated) to 700–740 × 460–470 mm (inflated), with a thickness up to 70 mm. Air pressure was adjusted manually and monitored using Bluetooth-connected differential sensors (Testo 510i, Testo AG, Switzerland; resolution: 0.001 kPa, accuracy: ±0.02 kPa + 1.5 %).

The investigation focuses on the interaction between two variables: weight and air pressure inside the air mattress. The weight included three discrete conditions. The lowest weight represents an early pre-term neonate, and the highest weight represents a term neonate (1.3 kg, 2.3 kg, 3.3 kg). The weights were anatomically distributed within the doll to reflect realistic neonatal body proportions. One quarter of the total weight was placed in the head, with the remainder assigned to trunk (30%), arms (20%), and legs (25%). This approach has been established in a previous study [12].

For each weight condition, four specific air pressures were investigated in steps of 0.1 kPa, to observe the interaction between weight and air pressure, ranging from 0.2 to 0.5 kPa (1.3 kg model), 0.3 to 0.6 kPa (2.3 kg), and 0.4 to 0.7 kPa (3.3 kg). A previous study [12] described the air pressure border conditions: bottoming-out in low air pressures and limitations in high air pressures. 0.4 and 0.5 kPa air pressure was measured in all doll weights. The following air pressure configurations were assessed. Comparisons with and without the pressure sensor mat were performed with 0.4 kPa air pressure.

Data processing

All data were processed using MATLAB (R2023b, MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA, USA) [25]. Interface pressure datasets were grouped by mattress type, air pressure setting, and body weight. To account for unequal sample sizes and to ensure robust results, Welch-corrected ANOVAs were used, although only one anatomical region violated the assumption of variance homogeneity. To assess the effect of air pressure on interface pressure, Welch-corrected one-way ANOVAs were performed. Pairwise

comparisons were performed using two-tailed Welch t-tests ($\alpha = 0.05$). All reported p-values from post-hoc and planned comparisons were adjusted for multiple testing using the Holm–Bonferroni method.

Exponential regression model to predict interface pressure

To determine the optimal air pressure setting for minimizing interface pressure depending on body weight, an exponential regression model was fitted to the interface pressure data obtained from point sensors positioned at the occiput and hip. The relationship between air pressure and interface pressure was modeled using an inverted Gaussian function (Eq. 1). The resulting three-dimensional regression model was defined as:

$$y(x, w) = a_1 - a_2 \cdot e^{\left(-\frac{(x-(x_0+b_2 \cdot w))^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} + b_1 \cdot w \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where y represents the predicted interface pressure [kPa]. x the applied air pressure [kPa], w the body weight [kg]. The other coefficients were fitted: a_1 and a_2 describe the upper plateau and the reduction amplitude of interface pressure, respectively. the term x_0 represents the baseline optimum air pressure, σ the curve width, b_1 a linear slope capturing the weight-dependent increase in interface pressure, and b_2 a linear shift in the air pressure minimum with weight. Model fitting was performed using constrained nonlinear least-squares optimization (lsqcurvefit) in MATLAB. Bounds and initial coefficient values were selected based on physiological plausibility and empirical stability. The coefficient of determination, adjusted R^2 , was calculated to evaluate goodness of fit.

To determine the optimal air pressure for a given body weight, the interface pressure function $y(x, w_0)$ was minimized by varying air pressure x within the measured range, using "fminbnd", constrained to the measured range (0.2–0.8 kPa). Region-specific models were created for the occiput and hip, and the resulting surfaces were visualized as 3D plots with a semi-transparent fit and superimposed experimental data.

Results

Influence of the pressure sensor mat

Data about the impact of the pressure sensing mat on interface pressures measured by the point pressure sensors is shown in Figure 2. Welch-ANOVA revealed significant effects of sensor mat application in all occiput conditions and in the hip region at 1.3 kg and 3.3 kg on the foam mattress, as well as at 3.3 kg on the air mattress. No significant differences were detected on the air mattress in the hip region at 1.3 kg and 2.3 kg, and on the foam mattress for 2.3 kg. For the foam mattress, we observed an increase in the point sensor measurement at the skin level when the sensor mat was added. The sensor mat increased point sensor interface pressure on both mattresses. On the air mattress, this occurred mainly at higher weights. On the foam mattress, the sensor mat increased point sensor values, especially at higher weights, while sensor mat values themselves stayed lower. At the hip, the sensor mat influenced point sensor interface pressure from mid to high weights, with no changes at the lowest weight.

Figure 2: Mean interface pressure (kPa) across three neonate doll weights (1.3kg, 2.3kg, 3.3kg) for foam and air mattresses with and without an additional pressure sensor mat, as well as detailed comparisons for the Occiput and Hip regions. Bars represent mean values with standard deviation; significance between conditions (with and without sensor mat, and between measurement methods) is indicated (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$ or "n.s." if not significant).

Effect of air pressure, weight, and anatomical region on interface pressure

To investigate the impact of varying air pressures on interface pressure in key body regions at risk, measurements without the sensor mat were compared to those on the foam mattress using Welch-corrected one-way ANOVA followed by post-hoc tests. Across all tested weights and anatomical sites, mean interface pressure was strongly affected by air pressure. A significant effect of air pressure ($F=146.57$, $df=64.92$, $p<0.01$) was confirmed. Pairwise comparisons revealed significant increases in interface pressure for all increasing air pressure level differences above 0.3 kPa ($p<0.01$), while differences between adjacent low pressure levels of 0.2 vs 0.3kPa were not different ($p=0.08$). Compared to the foam mattress, air pressures between 0.2 and 0.4 kPa consistently resulted in equal or lower interface pressure. At higher air pressures (≥ 0.5 kPa), interface pressures were higher than those of the foam mattress.

A two-way ANOVA identified significant main effects of body weight ($F(2,274)=192.02$, $p<0.01$) and anatomical region ($F(1,274)=22.88$, $p<0.01$) on interface pressure. No interaction was observed between weight and region ($F(2,274)=0.97$, $p=0.38$), indicating that weight-related changes in interface pressure were consistent across regions.

Levene tests showed no violation of variance homogeneity for the hip ($p=0.21$), but a significant violation for the occiput ($p=0.03$). Welch-corrected ANOVAs were applied for both regions to ensure robustness. These confirmed a significant weight effect in the hip ($F=59.98$, $df=105.12$, $p<0.01$) and occiput region ($F=164.07$, $df=156.39$, $p<0.01$).

Pairwise comparisons between all tested weights revealed significantly increased interface pressure with each weight increment ($p<0.01$).

Figure 3: The figure presents mean interface pressure values (kPa) for the foam mattress and the air mattress across multiple air pressures, separated by body region (top row: occiput, bottom row: hip) and weight (left to right: 1.3, 2.3, and 3.3kg). Holm-Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons within each weight group to adjust p-values from pairwise Welch t-tests (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$, or "n.s." if not significant).

Exponential regression model to predict interface pressure

The exponential regression model was fitted separately for the occiput (adjusted R^2 of 0.88, equation 2) and hip (adjusted R^2 was 0.92, Eq 3). For the occiput, the model resulted in an adjusted R^2 of 0.88. For the hip, the adjusted R^2 was 0.92. The fitted equation for the occiput was:

$$y(x, w) = 4.30 - 4.29 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{(x-(0.12+0.06 \cdot w))^2}{2 \cdot 0.30^2}\right)} + 1.09 \cdot w \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

And the equation for the hip:

$$y(x, w) = 5.40 - 4.50 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{(x-(0.19+0.06 \cdot w))^2}{2 \cdot 0.24^2}\right)} + 0.97 \cdot w \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

The predicted interface pressure values across the tested ranges of air pressure (0.2–0.8 kPa) and body weight (1.3–3.3 kg) were visualized as 3D surface plots. Higher air pressures consistently increased interface pressure across all weights. Differences between air pressure settings became more pronounced with weight, showing rising interface pressure with increasing air pressure. The minima of the fitted functions, representing the air pressure associated with the lowest predicted interface pressure for each weight, were determined by numerical minimization. The air pressure associated with the minimum interface pressure was 0.20 kPa at 1.3 kg, 0.26 kPa at 2.3 kg, and 0.32 kPa at 3.3 kg for the occiput (Figure 4A), and 0.26 kPa, 0.32 kPa, and 0.37 kPa, respectively, for the hip (Figure 4B).

Figure 4: Predicted interface pressure as a function of air pressure and body weight for [A] occiput and [B] hip, based on an exponential regression model fitted to point sensor measurements on the air mattress. The model combines an inverted Gaussian function with linear weight-dependent modulation of both the amplitude of interface pressure and air pressure. Each figure illustrates how interface pressure varies from 0.2 to 0.8 kPa inflation and body weight between 1.3 and 3.3 kg, enabling identification of the air pressure at which interface pressure is minimized for each body weight.

Discussion

Influence of using a pressure sensor mat

The investigation of local interface pressure using point sensors placed directly on the skin surface of a neonatal doll revealed systematic differences when compared to values recorded by a sensor mat positioned between the model and the support surface (Figure 2). Interface pressure significantly increased with body weight, as observed for both measurement systems. But findings also reveal how the measurement system itself can alter the mechanical interface conditions. When comparing the two measurement systems, point sensor values were considered to reflect more realistic values, as they are measuring the direct force impact on the level of the skin [26]. The sensor mat measures the forces on the mattress surface level. Differences between the two measuring systems were higher when measured on the foam mattress. In most cases, the values of the point sensor (with underlying sensor mat) were higher than the sensor mat values. This could indicate a systematic underestimation of interface pressure on the foam mattress with the sensor mat. Also, when using the air mattress, the results of the occiput area recorded by the sensor mat were significantly lower than the point sensor values at 1.3 kg. The lower values of interface pressure measured by the sensor mat might be attributed to pointy shapes of anatomical areas, such as the spherical shape of the occiput. At such shapes, the stiffness introduced by the sensor mat restricted localized immersion and altered load transfer, particularly on easily deformable surfaces like the air mattress. At low weights, this effect is amplified by a hammocking effect, where the sensor mat bridges across contours instead of conforming fully, reducing contact and lowering measured values [22]. The sensor mat influenced the properties of the deformable air-filled mattress more than those of the foam mattress, showing the importance of considering the influence of the mechanical properties of intermediate layers. The effect was particularly pronounced at higher weights, as shown by significant group differences by Welch-corrected ANOVA across all weights and regions ($p < 0.01$).

The point sensor captured a more consistent weight-dependent increase in interface pressure, especially at the hip on the air mattress (Figure 2). While point sensor values on the foam mattress at the occiput increased by $92\% \pm 24\%$ from 1.3 to 3.3 kg, the sensor mat recorded only a $40\% \pm 6\%$ increase under identical conditions. At the hip, both sensors showed comparable increases ($67\% \pm 22\%$ vs. $71\% \pm 15\%$, for the point sensor and sensor mat, respectively (Figure 2). On the air mattress, however, the sensor mat yielded a steeper increase at the occiput ($147\% \pm 35\%$) compared to the point sensor ($64\% \pm 33\%$). As for the head, a similar trend was observed for the hip, where increases of $25\% \pm 62\%$ for the sensor mat and $35\% \pm 15\%$ for the point sensor were observed. These variations underscore that surface properties influence not only absolute interface pressure values but also their scaling behavior with increasing body weight. Such effects might reflect the sensor mat's increased sensitivity to surface load, as its stiff material layer limits immersion and alters envelopment characteristics [27]. By adding a stiffer layer, the sensor mat modifies local deformation and shifts part of the load through tensile forces horizontally within its structure. It changes how weight is transmitted to the body and affects contact mechanics at the interface. Some load components may dissipate within the mat and remain unmeasured as normal interface pressure.

Clinical trials [28], [29], [30] relied on sensor mats to assess interface pressure. Current investigations show that sensor mats, particularly on foam mattresses, tend to underestimate actual skin-level interface pressure. As a result, foam mattresses may appear more effective in pressure distribution than they truly are. The findings are consistent with previous research [16], [31], [32]. Sensor bias requires systematic

correction based on sensor weight, body geometry, and support surface. Further research might account for shear components, as they contribute significantly to tissue deformation and injury [33].

Air pressures

The impact of the foam mattress and the multi-compartment air mattress, assessed with different target air pressures and different weight conditions, was investigated without the use of the pressure sensor mat. The interface pressure reduction on the air mattress was highly dependent on the interactions between air pressure, body region, and patient weight (Figure 3). As the air pressure controls mattress stiffness, it determines how effectively the load is reduced. This reveals under- and over-inflation effects, body region-specific optima, and a clinically relevant pressure range. At higher weight, higher air pressure was required to achieve sufficient load redistribution and prevent bottoming out. This pattern was especially evident at the hip. The occiput region responded strongly to low air pressures, particularly in the lightest condition tested. At 1.3 kg, interface pressure at the occiput was significantly reduced by air pressures as low as 0.2-0.3 kPa when compared to the foam mattress. This striking difference between the two regions likely reflects underlying anatomical and biomechanical principles: The hip, together with adjacent structures such as the back and thighs, engages a broad contact surface, allowing weight to distribute naturally across a large area. In contrast, the occiput concentrates approximately one-quarter of total body weight onto a small contact area at the posterior skull.

In neonates, where the skin is immature and protection through soft tissue is minimal, even small increases in local interface pressure may carry an elevated risk for tissue damage [34], [35]. The high anatomical vulnerability and minimal soft tissue coverage at the occiput make this region acutely sensitive to changes in mattress inflation. The pronounced occipital pressure reduction at low weight confirms that air mattresses, when correctly configured, can outperform foam in critical regions in neonates with low body weight.

Exponential regression model to predict interface pressure

The inverted Gaussian function represents a bell-shaped behavior between the two maximum interface pressures, as it is present on hard surfaces, i.e., a maximally inflated or completely deflated air mattress. Excessively inflated surfaces become rigid, diminishing their ability to conform to body contours and increasing peak pressure beneath bony prominences. In case of complete deflation, it is assumed that the material of the air mattress provides no support, causing the body to lie on an underlying hard surface. During inflation, the air mattress starts wrapping around the body contour, and with sufficient inflation, the body lifts off the ground. At the minimal air pressure required to achieve lift-off, the distinct minimum in the fitted Gaussian profile (minimal interface pressure) represents the optimal air pressure setting. With further inflation, the mattress progressively hardens as the material reaches its elastic limit, and interface pressure increases towards its maximum plateau, mimicking a saturation-like behavior. This U-shaped response confirms that both under- and over-inflation can increase interface pressure [36], allowing for optimization of the system by determining the minimum. While the minimal air pressure derived in the controlled laboratory setting reflects the well-defined lift-off threshold, in real-world conditions, posture shifts and movement with varying interface pressures necessitate targeting the highest pressure expected in all position and movement scenarios. Effective pressure reduction relies on precisely calibrated air pressure that aligns with individual weight, anatomy, and risk profile to avoid local bottoming out. Kawabata et al. reported that, in the lateral position, targeted increases in air pressure reduced peak interface pressure at the greater trochanter, suggesting that posture-specific adjustments may alter interface pressure [37]. However, their findings were based on healthy adults and did

not assess small body sizes. In contrast, our data in a supine neonatal setting shows that even modest over-inflation increases interface pressure, particularly in anatomically vulnerable regions like the occiput.

The magnitude of interface pressures correlates with body weight. Furthermore, heavier weights cause a higher local pressure and are more prone to bottoming out at low air pressures, e.g., weights of 3.3 kg or more at 0.2 kPa. This induces a rightward shift of the fitted curve towards a higher air pressure with increasing weight to ensure adequate lift-off.

Differences in model coefficients for the occiput (optimal air pressure at 0.12 kPa) and the hip region (optimal air pressure at 0.19 kPa) indicate anatomically specific surface interactions. For neonates, around three-quarters of the total body weight is concentrated in the trunk air segment, whereas around one-quarter of the body weight is caused by the head and affects the head segment. Additionally, the weight-dependent shift coefficient (b_2) was slightly larger for the occiput (0.060) than for the hip (0.055), suggesting that the occiput region requires proportionally greater increases in air pressure with rising body weight to ensure optimal support. This results from the high weight-to-surface-area ratio at the head, where a substantial portion of body weight is distributed over a small contact area, leading to elevated interface pressure. The curve width parameter of the curve (σ), influencing the sensitivity range of optimal pressures, displayed a broader curve for the occiput (0.30 kPa) compared to the hip (0.24 kPa). This indicates a slightly wider range of comfortable air pressures for the occiput. Apart from anatomical differences, this is possibly due to the geometry of the air segment. The head segment is rather large for the small contact area of the head; once the head is lifted off, an increase in air pressure causes a relatively small change in the small contact area. In contrast, the narrower optimal range at the hip reflects the critical need for precise air pressure settings due to a higher coverage of the mattress by the body contours. Furthermore, movements, such as a side rotation, could cause local bottoming out at low air pressures. The upper plateau of the curves (a_1) was higher for the hip (5.40) than the occiput (4.30). This is caused by the higher weight of the body segment, setting a higher interface pressure on the hip. This result is in line with the higher reduction of interface pressure by the air mattress on the head segment compared to the hip segment reported in a previously performed clinical trial [30].

Material skin interactions depend not only on direct surface interactions but are also influenced by material properties such as elasticity. Regarding the material composition, the air mattress used in this study was composed of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU), with specific elastic properties. Material elasticity critically influences the required air pressure for optimal patient support. In principle, mattresses with greater elasticity necessitate higher air pressures, as increased stretch will occur before adequately supporting and lifting the patient segment. Conversely, stiffer materials produce a faster and steeper rise in interface pressure as air pressure increases, resulting in narrower optimal pressure ranges and increased sensitivity to pressure adjustments. Consequently, differences in mattress material as well as sensor mat composition significantly alter the observed optimal air pressure ranges and associated physiological behaviors, highlighting the necessity for material-specific optimization of air mattress inflation protocols. This effect is exemplified by the fundamental contrast between foam and air systems: foam provides stable and constant support, while air systems offer mechanical tunability at the cost of requiring careful configuration. The advantage of adjustable air support lies in its ability to match changing physiological and anatomical demands, especially relevant in neonatal and pediatric care, where patient morphology evolves rapidly. Although this study focused on static supine positioning, the data clearly emphasize the necessity to precisely configure air pressure.

Limitations

This study focused on static supine positioning and measured normal forces at the skin interface, which differs from *in vivo* conditions. The mechanical property of the neonatal doll differs from that of real soft skin tissue. Its relatively stiff shell limits local deformation and may alter interface pressure transmission. In regions with small or curved contact areas, such as the occiput, slight shifts in point sensor placement can lead to substantial variability due to localized pressure peaks. Interface pressure alone cannot fully predict tissue breakdown, as dynamic conditions, shear forces, and internal physiological responses such as strain, perfusion, and capillary occlusion were not captured. These aspects should be addressed in future research. Future integration of physiological parameters will help clarify how mattress type, settings, and interface pressure contribute to tissue damage. Although difficult to assess in vulnerable populations, these factors are essential for developing effective prevention strategies in newborns.

Conclusions

This study quantified how interface pressure in neonatal models responds to changes in mattress type, air pressure, and the use of sensor mats. By incorporating nonlinear regression, a predictive model was established to describe interface pressure as a function of air pressure and body weight for the head and the hip area separately. A distinct anatomical sensitivity and weight-dependent pressure response was found. The data show that interface pressure does not change linearly with increased air pressure but follows an inverted Gaussian pattern, underscoring the need for precise air pressure control to minimize interface pressure.

Measurements with a sensor mat deviated systematically from skin-level values, especially under low-weight conditions and on soft, deformable support surfaces. These deviations confirm that measurement systems themselves can alter the mechanical interface they aim to assess, particularly when the interface compliance of the underlying mattress is high. This emphasizes the necessity for critical evaluation of sensing methods in neonatal care.

Together, these findings demonstrate the effect of a pressure sensor mat on the results themselves and offer a robust mechanical foundation for determining optimal air pressure levels that minimize interface pressure. The data enables specification of regional air pressure requirements and the design of neonatal air mattresses with spatially adaptive mechanical properties. This approach supports targeted offloading in anatomically vulnerable zones, addressing the specific loading risks faced by neonates.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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